

Assessment of Instructional Resources for Teaching and Learning of Basic Technology among Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was designed to investigate the assessment of basic Technology learning resources among Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. The research design that was adopted for this study is the descriptive survey method. Four research questions guided the study. The study population comprised all Basic technology teachers in Osun State while the purposive sampling technique was used to select 17 schools and 48 available teachers participated. An adapted questionnaire tagged Learning Resources Assessment Questionnaire (LRAQ) was used as the research instrument. Simple percentages, mean scores, and standard deviation were used to analyze the results. The findings showed that out of 26 learning resources that are required to be available in any secondary school to Basic Technology only 12 (46.2%) are available while 14 (53.8%) learning resources are not available. Some available learning resources are not adequate for teaching and learning Basic Technology, the available learning resources are occasionally used but not frequently used and the barriers to effective use of learning resources for teaching and learning of Basic Technology include low teachers' competence, poor teachers' professional knowledge, poor maintenance culture, non-availability of standard workshops, insufficient power supply, scarcity of teachers, lack of accessibility to learning resources, and resistance to change on the part of the teacher. Based on the findings, suggested recommendations include provision for adequate learning materials for the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria, which should be provided by the Ministry of Education and School Management

Keywords: Assessment, Learning resources, Basic Technology, Practical Skills, Metropolis

Introduction

Education globally is experiencing several reforms and the purpose of these reforms is to allow educational stakeholders to perform their responsibilities more efficiently. As a result, students are expected to be equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to deal with the ever-increasing challenges of the modern world. Technology has become an important part of most educational organizations all over the world. No doubt using technology tools provides productive teaching and learning to increase learners' creative and intellectual resources, especially in today's information society.

Technology is considered a step-by-step procedure, a systematic approach to an act to enhance the process of production. Akinde and Adetimirin (2017) described technology as a way of doing things leading to the development of processes and devices which is indispensable to the stable enhancement of the quality of life of human beings through the application of knowledge derived from systematic investigation of natural forces and materials. Nigeria as a country to realize accelerated development in the 21st century, needs qualitative science and technology education in our schools especially at the Junior Secondary Schools level which is invariably the foundation for advanced science and technology education. The Federal Government of Nigeria having realized that the level of utilizing technology of a nation determines the level of advancement and development of such a nation, made her approved the teaching of technological subjects in all the Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria and named it Introductory Technology now referred to as Basic Technology. Abdul-Ganiyu, Oyeronke, and Adunni (2019), regarded the inclusion of pre-vocational subjects in the Junior Secondary Schools curriculum as the greatest assets of the 9-3-4 system of curriculum.

Basic Technology is one of the pre-vocational subjects offered at the Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. It is a preparatory core subject of vocational and technical education. It comprises areas such as carpentry, joinery, masonry, machine fitting, metal fabrication, motor mechanics, automobile, and general works which are capable of equipping the students with the required job skills for self-reliance. The objectives of Basic Technology according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria include providing pre-vocational orientation for further training in technology; providing basic technological literacy for everyday living and stimulating creativity (FRN, 2013). The curriculum content of Basic Technology is designed to achieve these stated objectives.

Basic Technology being one of the skill-oriented subjects bearing in mind the above objectives enables the individual to acquire appropriate skills, abilities, and competence to live in and contribute effectively to the development of his society (Amosa, Ogunlade, and Atobatele, 2015). It is very important to note that without the knowledge of Basic Technology, Nigeria as a nation might be left behind in the scientific and technological race. This then means that there is a need for adequate commitment to the teaching and training of Basic Technology in our Junior Secondary Schools. The thoroughness in the teaching of introductory technology will lead to the accomplishment of the objectives of vocational and technical education programmes at the higher level of our educational system which is the major plight of Nigeria as a nation. Furtherance of our youths in the skills and other engineering-oriented courses at our tertiary level of education is highly dependent on their earlier knowledge and skills acquired at the secondary school level (Arop, Umanah, & Effiong, 2015). Looking at the alarming rate of unemployment in the country, the need for the nation to embrace the teaching and learning of vocational and technical courses in our schools towards building an individual for self-reliance should be given the utmost priority.

The subjects like Basic Technology whose goal is to expose students to the world of business, achievement scores only are insufficient to measure whether the goals of the subject have been achieved or not (Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, NERDC, 2013). Studies carried out by Okenjom, (2018), revealed that some students depend on rote memory that is, cramming facts and obtaining high scores rather than understanding Basic Technology concepts to reason out solutions. To achieve the acquisition of technical and practical skills at the lower craft level, the contributions of the teacher of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools are paramount. Students are expected to complete secondary school not only by having high scores in Basic Technology but being able to effectively apply the knowledge and competence gained in the classroom to solve personal and societal challenges (Onele, 2018). Subjects such as Basic Technology is practically oriented which requires that the students master the knowledge and skills for better performance in examinations. The emphasis laid on the transfer of basic skills in Basic Technology has placed much demand on the selection and application of appropriate learning materials and the use of the proper methodology in teaching.

Traditionally, teaching and learning of Basic Technology and other subjects in Nigerian schools are done in a structured way with emphasis on writing, reading, and listening to teachers' talk. National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (2013) however posited that teachers must diversify their teaching techniques if they are to successfully teach students of different abilities and learning preferences. Schools have therefore applied various approaches over the years in teaching students at various levels. It has been noted with dismay, however, that teachers are still using one or a combination of two or more conventional teaching methods such as lecture, discussion, and demonstration to teach Basic Technology without using appropriate learning materials (Omiola, Enuwa, Awoyemi, & Adebayo, 2012).

In developed countries, teachers use learning materials and new technologies to facilitate learning. These learning resources are produced and kept in educational resource centres (ERC) in all educational citadels of learning. Educational resources centres (ERC) are known by many names such as Audio-Visual Centres, Learning Resource Centres, Educational Technology Centres, and Instructional Resources Centre (Badmus, Adebajo & Ganiyu, 2021). In developing countries like Nigeria, research has it that 80% of teachers still make use of the conventional or traditional method of teaching to facilitate knowledge, this may look boring to the students after a while and the job of a teacher becomes only effective when he can pass knowledge to the students and the students is convinced by what is been delivered to them (Uche, Abdullahi, Asogwa, & Ofoegbu, 2016).

According to the NBTE (2013), Basic Technology deals with the fundamentals of engineering and technology which are to be taught as an integration of Technical Drawing, Building Construction, Woodwork, Metalwork, Electrical and Electronics, Automobile-mechanics, Food Technology and Computer Education. The inclusion of Basic Technology or Introductory Technology in the school curriculum calls for a well-planned curriculum and NERDC (2004) suggested some useful and relevant learning materials/resources to prevent the teacher from wasting much time in trying to explain concepts in abstract. They also suggested that there should be a shift in the focus of the conventional method of teaching Basic Technology to incorporate technological tools that would engage students in entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, the place of learning

resources in the successful implementation of curriculum cannot be over-emphasized as a channel through which information or messages can be disseminated to learners.

Qaiser, Hussain, Naseer, Din, and Khalid (2017) stated that learning resources are human and non-human materials supports or aids that a teacher uses to pass information to the students in the classroom. Apart from its ability to enhance the positive attitude of learners towards learning, it also helps them in making use of their various functioning sense organs to the maximum. According to Shazli (2019), human resources are support staff and subject matter experts who serve as resources for teachers and learners. These people have advanced knowledge and experience dealing with specialized learning resources for example Teachers, Technicians, Technologists, Workshop or Laboratory Attendants, Operators, other examples of learning resources that teachers often use are Textbooks, Chalkboards, Posters, Charts, Pictures, Computers, Flannels Graphs, Projectors, Radios, Televisions, audiovisual, Tapes, Workshops, Drawing Room, Transparencies, Machines, Hand Tools, Photographs, Models among others. All these are referred to as non-human resources. When these learning resources are being utilized properly, it helps minimize the problem of overpopulation and overcrowding in the classroom.

Simeon (2019) classified media (resources) into four; printed media, graphics, photography and electronics. Likewise, Abdu-Raheem (2016) agreed with this by classifying media (resources) into printed, projected (electronic), and non-projected media. When a medium of learning experience is well designed, produced, and validated, it becomes a valuable resource that has the flexibility of serving a single learner as well as a sizeable or large class of learners (Adekola, 2018). According to Adekunbi, (2018), learning resources are a broad range of information-carrying resources that constitute an integral component of classroom teaching and learning that are utilized in a learning process with the hope of facilitating effective and efficient communication in teaching and learning process. These are all information channel that is processed through the use of devices that could assist learners in seeing, hearing, feeling and in becoming aware and alive with the information being communicated to them. Therefore, for effective teaching of Basic Technology to take place, the use of learning resources cannot be compromised.

According to Matazu (2022), learning resources play an essential part in the teaching-learning processes among which are as follows: improving students' memory levels; making the teaching-learning process easier; increasing the rate of assimilation of students; serving as instruments for teachers to utilize in correcting incorrect impressions and illustrating ideas that students cannot easily forget; assist in giving the body of knowledge under debate a sense of actuality; it personalizes teaching and stimulates teachers' inventiveness; allow students and teachers to participate in concrete learning activities that develop the concept of self-evaluation. Hence, it is practically impossible to teach Basic Technology without learning resources. This is because they constitute an important component in the teaching and learning environment (Matazu, 2022). They can be regarded as the vehicle that carries messages or information from a transmitting source (teacher) to the receiver (learner). Salaudin, (2020) expressed those students cannot fully understand most of the concepts of Basic Technology when taught without learning resources. As a pre-vocational subject, Basic Technology must be taught practically and not only theoretically for it to be meaningful, understood, and appreciated by students. Teachers should therefore expect to emphasize the understanding of Basic Technology and not on collection of information or memorization.

Becta (2008), found that many secondary school teachers lacked the knowledge and skills to use learning resources most especially computers, and were not enthusiastic about the changes and integration of supplementary learning associated with bringing computers into their teaching practices. Sicilia (2015) found that the problem of lack of time exists for teachers in many aspects of their work as it affects their ability to complete tasks, with some of the participant teachers specifically stating which aspects of ICT require more time. These include the time needed to locate Internet advice, prepare lessons, explore and practice using the technology, deal with technical problems, and receive adequate training. Furthermore, the barrier most frequently referred to in the literature is the lack of effective training (Beggs, 2020).

Despite the introduction of Basic Technology, the aspiration for white-collar jobs and unemployment have persistently been on the increase. This problem has been attributed partly to poor teaching and learning methods which do not allow mastery of the contents adopted by the teachers in teaching Basic Technology. In an attempt to solve this problem, findings have revealed that students cannot fully understand most of the concepts of Basic Technology when taught without learning resources. Although previous studies have used different methods to improve student performance in this regard, persistence failure in Basic Technology is alarming and requires replicable solutions. As a pre-vocational subject, Basic Technology must be taught practically and not only theoretically for it to be meaningful, understood, and appreciated by students. The learning contents need to be incorporated with motivating components to stimulate students' creativity and engage them with the content of the subject. This would strengthen students' capabilities to effectively apply the knowledge and competence gained in the classroom to solve personal and societal challenges. Public Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria, still find it difficult to make available some learning resources probably due to cost implications or the stress embedded in the acquisition

of those resources at the detriment of students' optimal academic performance (Ajadi, 2016). In some cases, those who even have learning facilities are not judiciously making use of them due to a lack of appropriate knowledge of their usage by the teachers, especially electronic-aided facilities like computers and other internet-enabling devices (Afolabi, 2020).

Hence, the need to investigate demystifying Basic Technology by making it more interesting, engaging, friendly, and applicable to real-life situations to stimulate students' creativity and better academic understanding is to ensure the learning resources are available, utilized, and frequently used. Given the foregoing, the study was set to investigate the assessment of learning resources for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

This research aimed to assess the basic technology learning resources among junior secondary schools in Osogbo metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

1. identify available learning resources for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.
2. determine whether the available learning resources are adequate for the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.
3. assess how frequently the available learning resources are used for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria, and
4. investigate barriers to the use of learning resources in the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What learning resources are available for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are available learning resources adequate for the teaching of Basic Technology in your school?
3. How frequently are the available learning resources utilized for teaching Basic Technology in Junior schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?
4. What are the barriers to the use of learning resources in teaching and learning of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey method. The population for this study consists of all Basic Technology teachers at the Junior Secondary Schools across Osun State.

A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select Basic Technology teachers because in a school these teachers are not many so the available Basic Technology teachers were used for the study. A total of seventeen (17) secondary schools in Osogbo Metropolis were purposively selected due to the presence of Introductory Technology laboratories in the schools. In all, 48 Basic Technology teachers are available in these schools and participated as respondents.

The research instrument that was used for the study was a structured questionnaire adapted from Lawrence Femi Ademiluyi, (2019). This study research instrument titled "Learning Resources Assessment Questionnaire (LRAQ)" which comprises five (5) sections: Section A, B, C, D, and E. Section A borders on demographic information of the respondents; Section B focuses on the availability of learning resources; Section C deals with adequacy of learning resources; Section D centered on the frequency of use of learning resources while Section E sought for the factors or barriers to the use of learning resources.

The instrument was given to four experts for face and content validity, two experts from Basic Technology, one from Educational Technology, and one from Educational Evaluation. Their comments and observations were incorporated into the final copy of the instrument before it was administered. Thus, this improved the quality of the instrument. The instrument was piloted and processed for a reliability test. It was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient yielded 0.76.

Descriptive statistics like frequency distribution, simple percentages, mean score, and standard deviation were used to address the stated research questions through the use of SPSS.

Results

Research Question 1: What types of learning resources are available for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Available Learning Resources for Teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary School

S/N	Learning Resources	%		%		Decision
		Available	Not Available	Available	Not Available	
1	Workshop	32	66.7	16	33.3	Available
2	Hammer	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
3	Saw	34	70.8	14	29.2	Available
4	Hand file	28	58.3	20	41.7	Available
5	Pliers	32	66.7	16	33.3	Available
6	Try-Square	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
7	Circular Saw	8	16.7	40	83.3	Not Available
8	Surface Planner	12	25.0	36	75.0	Not Available
9	Thickneser	34	70.8	14	29.2	Available
10	Wood lathe	16	33.3	32	66.7	Not Available
11	Centre lathe	11	22.9	37	77.1	Not Available
12	Power Saw	10	20.8	38	79.2	Not Available
13	Pedestal grinder	23	47.9	25	52.1	Not Available
14	Milling Machine	9	18.8	39	81.2	Not Available
15	Learning Audio Tape	18	37.5	30	62.5	Not Available
16	Television/Monitor Set	21	43.7	27	56.3	Not Available
17	Audio C.D's on Technology	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
18	Video Players & Recorders	10	20.8	38	79.2	Not Available
19	Computer (Monitor, C.P.U & Printers)	14	29.2	34	70.8	Not Available
20	Projectors	5	10.4	43	89.6	Not Available
21	Video CDs	15	31.2	33	68.8	Not Available
22	Chalkboard	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available
23	Wall Posters on Technology	40	83.3	8	16.7	Available
24	Photographs on Technology	34	70.8	14	29.2	Available
25	Models on Technology	20	41.7	28	58.3	Not Available
26	Printed Media (Textbooks & Workbook)	36	75.0	12	25.0	Available

Source: Fieldwork

Table 1 revealed that learning resources like circular saws, surface planers, wood lathes, power saws, centre lathes, milling machines, video player recorders, computers, projectors, wall posters, and models are not available in the school to teach Basic Technology, this is because the percentage scores of those learning resources are below 50% which is the middle percentage of 100. Learning resources like workshops, hammers, saws, handfiles, pliers, try-square, thicknessers, chalkboards, wall posters, photographs, models, and printed media are available to use. The implication of the results showed out of 26 learning resources 12 are available while 14 learning resources are not available.

Research Question 2: To what extent are available learning resources adequate for the teaching of Basic Technology in your school?

Table 2: Adequacy of Available Learning Resources for Teaching and Learning of Basic Technology

S/N	Learning Resources	Adequate	%	Inadequate	%	Decision
1	Workshop	28	58.3	20	41.7	Adequate

2	Hammer	32	66.7	16	33.3	Adequate
3	Saw	12	25.0	36	75.0	Not Adequate
4	Hand file	40	83.3	8	16.7	Adequate
5	Pliers	34	70.8	14	29.2	Adequate
6	Try-Square	20	41.7	28	58.3	Not Adequate
7	Circular Saw	2	4.2	46	95.8	Not Adequate
8	Surface Planner	5	10.4	43	89.6	Not Adequate
9	Thicknesser	16	33.3	32	66.7	Not Adequate
10	Wood lathe	34	70.8	14	29.2	Adequate
11	Centre lathe	2	4.2	46	95.8	Not Adequate
12	Power Saw	7	14.6	41	85.4	Not Adequate
13	Pedestal grinder	36	75.0	12	25.0	Adequate
14	Milling Machine	6	12.5	42	87.5	Not Adequate
15	Learning Audio Tape	36	75.0	12	25.0	Adequate
16	Television/Monitor Set	22	45.8	26	54.2	Not Adequate
17	Audio C.D's on Technology	32	66.7	16	33.3	Adequate
18	Video Players & Recorders	19	39.6	29	60.4	Not Adequate
19	Computer (Monitor, C.P.U & Printers)	28	58.3	20	41.3	Adequate
20	Projectors	3	6.3	45	93.7	Not Adequate
21	Video CDs	32	66.7	16	33.3	Adequate
22	Chalkboard	36	75.0	12	25.0	Adequate
23	Wall Posters on Technology	38	79.2	10	20.8	Adequate
24	Photographs on Technology	34	70.8	14	29.2	Adequate
25	Models on Technology	16	33.3	32	66.7	Not Adequate
26	Printed Media (Textbooks & Workbook)	40	83.3	8	16.7	Adequate

Source: Field work

Table 3 shows that learning resources such as circular saw, surface planer, wood lathe, centre lathe, power saw, milling machine, learning audio tape, video player computers, projector, video CD and models are not adequate to teach Basic Technology to Junior Secondary students. Out of 26 learning resources examined 14 were adequate while 12 learning resources were not adequate because their percentages were below 50%.

Research Question 3: How frequent are the available learning resources utilized for teaching Basic Technology in Junior secondary schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Frequent Use of Learning Resources to Teach Basic Technology

S/N	Learning Resources	Frequently		Occasionally		Rarely		Never		Mean Score	Std. Dev.
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		
1	Workshop	20	41.7	11	22.9	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.896	1.134
2	Hammer	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.016
3	Saw	14	29.2	17	35.5	5	10.4	12	25.0	2.688	1.151
4	Hand file	10	20.8	9	18.8	20	41.7	8	16.7	2.417	1.028
5	Pliers	25	52.1	12	25.0	8	16.7	3	6.3	3.229	0.951
6	Try-Square	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
7	Circular Saw	5	10.4	10	20.8	16	33.3	17	35.4	2.063	0.998

8	Surface Planner	3	6.3	4	8.3	25	52.1	15	33.3	1.875	0.815
9	Thickneser	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
10	Wood lathe	5	10.4	3	6.3	23	47.9	17	35.4	1.917	0.919
11	Centre lathe	2	4.2	5	10.4	17	20.8	24	64.6	1.542	0.849
12	Power Saw	5	10.4	5	10.4	10	20.8	28	58.3	1.729	1.026
13	Pedestal grinder	7	14.6	8	16.7	25	52.1	5	16.7	2.292	0.922
14	Milling Machine	2	4.2	9	18.8	25	52.1	12	25.0	2.021	0.785
15	Learning Audio Tape	9	18.8	5	10.4	17	35.4	17	35.4	2.125	1.104
16	Television/Monitor Set	10	20.8	9	18.8	20	41.7	8	16.7	2.417	1.028
17	Audio CD's on Technology	25	52.1	12	25.0	8	16.7	3	6.3	3.229	0.951
18	Video Players & Recorders	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
19	Computer (Monitor, C.P.U & Printers)	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.016
20	Projectors	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
21	Video CDs	14	29.2	17	35.5	5	10.4	12	25.0	2.688	1.151
22	Chalkboard	10	20.8	9	18.8	20	41.7	8	16.7	2.417	1.028
23	Wall Posters on Technology	25	52.1	12	25.0	8	16.7	3	6.3	3.229	0.951
24	Photographs on Technology	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.017
25	Models on Technology	20	41.7	10	20.8	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.854	1.167
26	Printed Media (Textbooks & Workbook)	17	35.5	14	29.2	12	25.0	5	10.4	2.896	1.016
Grand Mean Average									2.563		

Source: Field work

Table 3 revealed that the average mean score obtained was 2.563 which is slightly above 2.5 mid-point. The implication of this is that learning resources for teaching and learning Basic Technology are occasionally used but not frequently used.

Research Question 4: What are the barriers to the use of learning resources in teaching Basic Technology in Junior secondary schools in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Barriers to the Use of Learning Resources in Basic Technology in Schools

S/N	ITEM	SA		A		D		SD		Mean	Std D.
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%		
1	Low teacher competence in effective learning resource utilization negatively affects teaching outcome	20	41.7	4	8.3	13	27.1	11	22.9	2.313	1.240
2	Poor teacher's professional knowledge and technical know-how to teach practical skill content areas of Basic Technology leads to low utilization of learning materials	26	54.2	10	20.8	6	12.5	6	12.5	1.833	1.079
3	Poor maintenance culture of existing learning materials especially projected and manipulative types hinders the utilization of learning materials	27	56.3	10	20.8	5	10.0	5	10.4	1.771	1.036
4	Non-availability of standard and functional workshops greatly affects										

	the teaching and learning of Basic Technology	21	43.8	10	20.8	8	16.7	9	18.8	2.104	1.173
5	Insufficient power supply makes the operating of available Basic Technology equipment difficult	21	43.8	3	6.3	13	27.1	11	22.9	2.293	1.254
6	The scarcity of Basic Technology teachers in Junior Secondary Schools constitutes great problems in instructional delivery	18	37.5	13	27.1	9	18.8	8	16.7	2.146	1.111
7	Basic Technology teachers develop apathy to workshop practice due to lack of motivation.	24	50.0	8	16.7	8	16.7	8	16.7	2.000	1.167
8	Lack of accessibility to learning resources	21	43.8	15	31.3	8	16.7	4	8.3	1.896	0.973
9	Resistance to change from traditional methods	17	35.4	9	18.8	12	25.0	10	20.8	2.313	1.170
10	Lack of opportunities for in-service trainings for Basic Technology teachers to update their knowledge on resource development leads to poor utilization of learning materials in the teaching of the subject	24	50.0	8	16.7	6	12.5	10	20.8	2.042	1.219
11	Lack of finance to acquire needed learning materials impacts negatively on the teaching and learning of Basic Technology	21	43.8	16	33.3	4	8.3	7	14.6	1.938	1.060
12	Teachers are faced with insufficient time allocation to accommodate effective learning materials utilization in Basic Technology	21	43.8	12	25.0	9	18.8	6	12.5	2.000	1.072
Grand Mean Score		2.054									

Source: Fieldwork

Table 4 revealed that virtually all the statements are considered as factors or barriers to the use of learning resources for effective teaching and learning of Basic Technology. The grand mean score obtained is 2.054 which is below 2.5 of the mid-point of 4. The result implies that low teachers' competence, poor teachers' professional knowledge, poor maintenance culture, non-availability of standard workshops, insufficient power supply, scarcity of teachers, lack of accessibility to learning resources, and resistance to change on the part of the teacher are all barriers to the effective use of learning resource for teaching and learning of Basic Technology.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis of data, findings from this study showed that some of the important learning resources were not available for teaching Basic Technology in Junior Schools in Osogbo Metropolis. This result was in line with the outcome of the study of Okoji and Olubayo (2021) which revealed that not all the relevant learning resources are available to teach students in primary schools. Cohen, Raudenbush, and Ball (2012) whose study found that some learning resources are available while others are not. Chukwu, Eze, and Agada (2016) revealed that there is little extent of availability of instructional materials in junior secondary schools (upper basic) in the Enugu education zone.

The study found that available learning resources are not adequate for teaching and learning of Basic Technology and this finding is in line with the results of Okoli and Okorie (2015) in their study which revealed that business studies education facilities are lowly adequate, and compliant textbooks are lowly adequate. Okoroma (2006) also agreed that learning materials are in short supply in Nigerian secondary schools.

The outcome revealed 48 Basic Technology teachers who frequently access and confirm the available learning resources used for teaching Basic Technology in your school. Findings have revealed that teachers in Nigeria's public schools do not explore to the fullest the use of the educational media accessible for both teaching and learning the result was in line with Abdelraheem and Al-Rabani (2005) who found out that learning resources in schools are not well-utilized to expectation to improve learning outcome.

In the study, it was revealed that barriers to effective use of learning resources for teaching and learning of Basic Technology include low teachers' competence, poor teachers' professional knowledge, poor maintenance culture, non-availability of standard workshops, insufficient power supply, scarcity of teachers, lack of accessibility to learning resources, and resistance to change on the part of the teacher. The findings were supported by the finding of Elom (2014) which stated that factors militating against the teaching of Basic Technology in Abakaliki areas of Ebonyi State include outdated methods of teaching, ill-equipment in the workshops, no practical lessons for students, funding and financing are improperly done.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the availability of learning materials influences teaching Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo metropolis of Osun state. However, lack of accessibility to learning resources has been seen as one of the factors hindering Basic Technology teachers from using learning materials for Basic Technology teaching. In addition, some of the required learning resources to carry out effective teaching and learning of Basic Technology are fairly available while others are not. These fairly available learning resources are not regularly utilized by Basic Technology teachers. Several factors were found to inhibit effective provision and utilization of learning resources, among the factors are non-availability of standard and functional workshop which greatly affect the teaching and learning of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools in Osogbo metropolis of Osun State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the researcher recommends as follows:

1. Adequate learning materials for the teaching of Basic Technology in Junior Secondary Schools should be provided by the Ministry of Education and School Management.
2. Basic Technology teachers should make efforts in the utilization of available learning resources and endeavour to improvise those not available or inadequate to improve learning and make the subject attractive through involving the students in practical sessions.
3. Students should also be involved in the improvisation and use of learning resources as they learn more from what they do.
4. Training and retraining must be provided for teachers who are to teach Basic Technology using learning resources to assist them in acquiring necessary skills.

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